

EFFECTIVENESS OF STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS (SIMS) IN TEACHING CONJUNCTIONS AND MODALS AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) in improving the grammar proficiency of Grade 10 students, specifically in the use of conjunctions and modals. A quasi-experimental design, specifically the One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design, was employed. Participants were purposively selected Grade 10 students who had failed to meet the minimum mastery level in the summative test on conjunctions and modals. The SIMs, developed in accordance with DepEd standards, were validated by experts and implemented over a five-week intervention period. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, dry run and test-retest methods were conducted. Data were analyzed using statistical tools such as the percent, mean, and t-test for dependent data. The results indicated significant improvement in students' grammar skills, with proficiency in conjunctions and modals advancing from a fairly satisfactory level to an advanced level. This improvement was statistically significant, with a large effect size, confirming the positive impact of SIMs on students' ability to grasp grammar concepts. Additionally, students expressed very high perceptions of the benefits of SIMs, highlighting their effectiveness in enhancing motivation and engagement in grammar learning.

Keywords: *conjunctions, grammar proficiency, modals, remediation, Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs)*

INTRODUCTION

Mastery of grammar is widely acknowledged as a fundamental component of language education, playing a critical role in enabling students to communicate effectively in both academic and professional settings. According to Akhmadjonova (2024), a strong command of grammar enhances clarity and coherence in oral and written communication, contributing significantly to students' success across various domains. The World Bank (2022) emphasizes that foundational literacy, which includes grammatical competence, is vital in preparing learners for the demands of higher education and the workforce. However, learning disruptions during the post-pandemic period have increased existing challenges in grammar acquisition, resulting in considerable declines in English proficiency among K–12 students worldwide (WIDA, 2023). These challenges call for urgent, targeted, and sustainable instructional interventions.

In the Philippine context, grammar proficiency holds particular significance, given that English is both an official language and the primary medium of instruction across numerous academic disciplines. Despite the country's efforts to improve English instruction, the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries in the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), underscoring ongoing deficiencies in students' foundational language skills (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2023). Dizon and Villanueva (2022) noted that many Filipino students continue to struggle with the correct use of grammar, especially in areas such as sentence construction, logical connectors, and modal expressions. These persistent gaps in language skills impede learners' overall language development and academic performance.

Recognizing these instructional challenges, this study introduces teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) as a focused response to the grammar difficulties experienced by Grade 10 students, particularly in conjunctions and modals. Unlike interventions that rely heavily on digital platforms (Treceñe et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2020), this study provides a low-technology, classroom-based approach that is inclusive and accessible to students in under-resourced educational environments. The SIMs were carefully designed by the researcher, guided by pedagogical expertise ensuring alignment with both student needs and curriculum standards.

This initiative also supports Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education, particularly Target 4.1, which seeks to ensure that all learners acquire strong foundational skills through equitable and quality education. By offering context-appropriate instructional materials, the study promotes inclusive practices in language education and aims to reduce disparities in student performance, especially among those in low-resource schools. Additionally, it aligns with SDG Target 4.5, which focuses on eliminating disparities in access to effective learning tools and resources.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Strategic Intervention Materials in improving students' understanding and use of conjunctions and modals. By addressing these often-overlooked components of grammar through structured and accessible materials, the research contributes to evidence-based strategies for enhancing English

proficiency. As a language educator, the researcher highlights the importance of closing learning gaps through tailored interventions that foster academic growth, communicative competence, and lifelong learning—core principles of Sustainable Development Goal 4.

Research Questions

This study aims to develop and assess the effectiveness of teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) in enhancing Grade 10 students' grammatical proficiency, particularly on conjunctions and modals.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' level of grammar skills before the utilization of the SIMs in the following areas:
 - 1.1 conjunctions;
 - 1.1.1 coordinating conjunctions;
 - 1.1.2 subordinating conjunctions;
 - 1.1.3 correlative conjunctions;
 - 1.2 modals;
 - 1.2.1 modal verbs; and
 - 1.2.2 modal adverbs?
2. What is the level of grammar skills of the students in the same areas after the utilization of the SIMs?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of grammar skills of the students before and after the utilization of the SIMs?
4. To what extent do students perceive the benefits of the SIMs in learning grammar?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the level of grammar skills of the students before and after the utilization of the SIMs.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically the One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design. This design involved a single group of participants who completed a pretest before the intervention (Strategic Intervention Materials) and a posttest afterward. The pretest assessed the students' initial grammar proficiency, while the posttest measured any improvements resulting from the intervention.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in a school in Bayawan City, Negros Oriental, Philippines. The school serves a diverse student population, offering education to learners from various socio-economic backgrounds. The school is committed to improving academic performance through a range of intervention programs, with a particular focus on enhancing language skills. The research was carried out during the 2024-2025 academic year, concentrating on improving grammar proficiency through the use of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs). The school's infrastructure, along with its access to educational resources, provided an ideal setting for the successful implementation of the intervention and supported the research process.

Research Respondents

The study involved Grade 10 students who scored below the 75 percent standard criterion in the summative test on conjunctions and modals. A total of 13 students were purposively selected to participate in the study during the school year 2024-2025. These students were identified based on their need for additional support in grammar, specifically in conjunctions and modals, as demonstrated by their performance in the test.

Statistical Tools

The tools that were used by the researcher in analyzing the data are the following:

Percent. This was used to determine how a part was related to a whole. It was also used to identify whether the respondents had successfully passed or failed the intervention process.

Mean. This was used to identify the level of grammar skills of the students before and after the utilization of the SIMs. This was also utilized to examine the extent of benefits of the SIMs in learning grammar.

t-test for dependent data. This was used in identifying the significant differences in the pre-test and post-test performance of the students. This was selected since the data are in ratio scale.

The following scales were utilized to describe the benefits of the SIM:

Score	Scale	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	The student demonstrates a very high level of agreement (81%–100%) with the perceived benefits of SIM.
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	The student demonstrates a high level of agreement (61%–80%) with the perceived benefits of SIM.

3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	The student demonstrates a moderate level of agreement (41%–60%) with the perceived benefits of SIM.
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	The student demonstrates a low level of agreement (21%–40%) with the perceived benefits of SIM.
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	The student demonstrates a very low level of agreement (1%–20%) with the perceived benefits of SIM.

The students' proficiency in grammar skills particularly in conjunctions and modals is determined based on the adapted criteria set by DepEd under D.O. No. 8, s. 2015.

Rating	Verbal Equivalent	Explanation
95%–100%	Outstanding	Consistently demonstrates exceptional performance in grammar exams. Accurately applies conjunctions and modals in complex sentences, showing mastery in their correct usage across various contexts.
90%–94%	Advanced	Performs very well in grammar exams, with mostly accurate responses. Uses conjunctions and modals correctly in different sentence structures, with only minor errors in complex applications.
85%–89%	Very Satisfactory	Shows solid performance in exams. Correctly applies most conjunctions and modals but may occasionally misuse them in compound and complex sentences.
80%–84%	Satisfactory	Demonstrates adequate grammar knowledge. Uses basic conjunctions and modals correctly but struggles with advanced structures and proper contextual application.
75%–79%	Fairly Satisfactory	Shows limited understanding of conjunctions and modals. Makes frequent errors in their usage, especially in forming compound or conditional sentences.
74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations	Performs poorly in grammar exams. Struggles to use conjunctions and modals correctly, leading to sentence errors and unclear meanings. Needs focused intervention and support.

Research Instruments

The study utilized teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) to re-teach the least mastered skills, specifically conjunctions and modals. Three experts in English education validated the SIMs, following the Standard Criterion for SIMs (DepEd Memo No. 225, series of 2009, Enclosure No. 2). Revisions were made based on their feedback to enhance the SIMs' effectiveness and alignment with student needs.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument measuring the perceived effectiveness of the SIMs, a dry run was conducted with the researcher's former students at Tayawan National High School. The data were analyzed using the Cronbach's Alpha Test, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.705, indicating acceptable internal consistency.

For the grammar test used in both the pre-test and post-test, the test-retest method was applied, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.701, which indicates acceptable stability over time.

Following these validation and reliability procedures, a 100-item pre-test was administered, with 20 items per grammar category (Coordinating Conjunctions, Subordinating Conjunctions, Correlative Conjunctions, Modal Verbs, and Modal Adverbs). After the SIM intervention, participants took the same post-test. The pre-test and post-test scores were analyzed to assess the effectiveness of the intervention.

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

The study focused on conjunctions and modals, identified as the least mastered skills through the analysis of the Second Periodic Test. The researcher purposively selected 13 students who scored below the 75% Mean Percentage Score (MPS). In response to the identified learning gaps, the researcher developed Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) specifically targeting conjunctions and modals. These SIMs were validated by a panel of experts in English education, including the Education Program Supervisor for English, a PhD in Applied Linguistics, and the school's English Coordinator. The SIMs included the following components: the Title Card (presenting the topic and competency), the Task Card (outlining learning objectives and tasks), the Guide Card (explaining concepts through definitions and examples), the Activity Card (featuring scaffolded exercises), the Assessment Card (with quizzes to evaluate comprehension), the Enrichment Card (offering real-world applications), and the Answer Card (providing answers with brief explanations for self-checking). The SIMs were printed and distributed to the students, who participated in daily one-hour sessions during their free time for five weeks. Progress was monitored through pre-test and post-test scores, with descriptive statistics and paired sample t-tests used to analyze the data.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) in improving grammar proficiency among Grade 10 students, specifically in conjunctions and modals. The study targeted 13 students who scored below 75% in these areas. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combined a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design with qualitative interviews. Several limitations were identified: the small sample size of 13 students limits the generalizability of the results, and the focus on conjunctions and modals restricts the findings to these areas. The intervention took place during students' vacant periods, which impacted attendance, motivation, and task completion. Variability in student engagement due to extracurricular activities and home

responsibilities further influenced participation. Lastly, as the study was conducted in a single public high school, the findings may not be applicable to other educational settings.

RESULTS

Table 1. Students' Level of Grammar Skills before the Utilization of the SIMs (n=13)

Topics	\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Standard Deviation
Conjunctions			
• Coordinating Conjunctions	85.58	Very Satisfactory	5.88
• Subordinating Conjunctions	75.77	Fairly Satisfactory	5.72
• Correlative Conjunctions	71.92	Did Not Meet Exp.	8.73
Modals			
• Modal Verbs	76.73	Fairly Satisfactory	9.43
• Modal Adverbs	78.85	Fairly Satisfactory	6.34
Overall	77.77	Fairly Satisfactory	5.51

Table 1 shows the grammar skills of Grade 10 students in conjunctions and modals before using Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs). The overall average rating of 77.77 indicates that students have a fairly satisfactory level of grammar proficiency. Specifically, students performed very well in coordinating conjunctions but had only fairly satisfactory scores in subordinating conjunctions, modal verbs, and modal adverbs. However, students did not meet the expected level in correlative conjunctions, highlighting an area needing improvement.

Table 2. Students' Level of Grammar Skills after the Utilization of the SIMs (n = 13)

Topics	\bar{x}	Verbal Description	Standard Deviation
Conjunctions			
• Coordinating Conjunctions	92.31	Advanced	5.72
• Subordinating Conjunctions	88.27	Very Satisfactory	5.81
• Correlative Conjunctions	87.69	Very Satisfactory	7.46
Modals			
• Modal Verbs	88.27	Very Satisfactory	4.72
• Modal Adverbs	91.15	Advanced	7.61
Overall	89.57	Advanced	5.59

Table 2 presents the grammar skills of Grade 10 students after the utilization of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs). The overall mean score increased to 89.57, reflecting advanced proficiency. Students achieved advanced proficiency levels in coordinating

conjunctions (92.31) and modal adverbs (91.15). Additionally, very satisfactory ratings are obtained in subordinating conjunctions (88.27), correlative conjunctions (87.69), and modal verbs (88.27).

Table 3. *Difference in the Level of Grammar Skills of the Students before and after the Utilization of the SIMs (n = 13)*

Topics	Before	After	D	t	p	Remark	Effect Size
Conjunctions							
• Coordinating Conjunctions	85.58	92.31	5.39	4.386	<.001	Significant	1.217
• Subordinating Conjunctions	75.77	88.27	10.00	7.464	<.001	Significant	2.070
• Correlative Conjunctions	71.92	87.69	12.61	6.640	<.001	Significant	1.842
Modals							
• Modal Verbs	76.73	88.27	9.24	5.791	<.001	Significant	1.606
• Modal Adverbs	78.85	91.15	9.84	6.672	<.001	Significant	1.851
Overall	77.77	89.57	9.44	11.630	<.001	Significant	3.225

Level of significance = 0.05; Cohen's d Effect Size Interpretation: d=0.2 (small); d=0.5 (medium); d =0.8 (large)

Table 3 presents the differences in students' grammar skills before and after using Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs). A paired t-test analysis reveals significant improvements in all grammatical areas assessed, including conjunctions (coordinating, subordinating, and correlative) and modals (modal verbs and modal adverbs). Specifically, coordinating conjunctions improved from 85.58 to 92.31, subordinating conjunctions from 75.77 to 88.27, and correlative conjunctions from 71.92 to 87.69. Similarly, modal verbs increased from 76.73 to 88.27 and modal adverbs from 78.85 to 91.15. All improvements were statistically significant with p-values of <.001, well below the 0.05 significance level.

Table 4. *Extent of Benefits of the SIMs in Learning Grammar (n = 13)*

Statements	\bar{x}	VD	EoB	SD
1. I want to use SIM during remediation class	5.00	SA	VH	0.00
2. The SIM helps me better understand the types and usage of conjunctions and modal verbs.	4.92	SA	VH	0.28
3. SIM inspired and encouraged me to learn grammar.	4.92	SA	VH	0.28
4. Confusing concepts of conjunctions and modals were clearly presented.	4.85	SA	VH	0.38
5. The presentation of the grammar lesson in the SIM is fitted to my needs.	4.85	SA	VH	0.38

6. The instructions are simple and easy to follow.	4.85	SA	VH	0.38
7. The SIM is a student-friendly material,	4.85	SA	VH	0.38
8. Activities and tasks given in the SIM are easy and fun.	4.77	SA	VH	0.44
9. I could easily understand the explanation and examples provided in the SIM.	4.77	SA	VH	0.44
10. I can set up my own pace in learning the topics without being pressured with time.	4.62	SA	VH	0.51
Composite	4.84	SA	VH	0.34

Table 4 presents the extent of benefits of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) in teaching conjunctions and modals. The results indicate a very high (VH) extent of benefits, as reflected in the composite mean score of 4.84, which falls under the Strongly Agree (SA) category. The highest-rated statement ($\bar{x} = 5.00$) highlights the very strong preference for using SIMs during remediation classes, suggesting their effectiveness in reinforcing grammar lessons. These findings align with the study of Bacatan et al. (2022), which reported that students found SIMs helpful in understanding previously challenging topics and teachers supported the use of SIMs, emphasizing their usefulness for students with learning difficulties.

DISCUSSION

Students' Level of Grammar Skills before the Utilization of the SIMs

The pretest results suggest that although Grade 10 students have a basic understanding of conjunctions and modals, their knowledge is incomplete, especially in the correct use and differences between various grammar forms. Their difficulty with correlative conjunctions points to gaps in basic grammar knowledge, which may result from traditional teaching methods not fully addressing students' learning needs. This observation matches earlier research by Dumape (2020), who noted similar gaps in grammar skills among Grade 10 students. Additionally, studies by Belarmino (2024) and Irawan and Wahyudi (2022) reported similar findings, showing students scoring below satisfactory levels in pre-tests. Overall, these studies emphasize the importance of using targeted interventions like SIMs to close these gaps and improve students' grammar skills.

Students' Level of Grammar Skills after the Utilization of the SIMs

The posttest results clearly indicate that generally, students perform very well in grammar exams, with mostly accurate responses. They use conjunctions and modals correctly in different sentence structures, with only minor errors in complex applications. This performance suggests that SIMs provided structured, engaging, and effective learning experiences, enabling students to grasp and correctly apply grammatical concepts in various contexts. The positive change underscores the effectiveness of SIMs as instructional tools in enhancing grammar proficiency.

These findings align with previous studies that highlight the effectiveness of SIMs. Dumape (2020) similarly reported improvements in students' grammar performance after employing SIMs. Furthermore, Sebulen et al. (2023) observed notable increases in grammar post-test scores, further reinforcing the importance and effectiveness of SIMs in bridging learning gaps and promoting higher academic achievement.

Level of Grammar Skills of the Students before and after the Utilization of the SIMs

The calculated effect sizes (Cohen's d) indicate large effects in all grammar topics, particularly notable in the overall grammar skills ($d = 3.225$), emphasizing the substantial positive impact of SIMs. These results strongly support the effectiveness of SIMs in significantly enhancing students' grammar proficiency.

These findings align with previous studies. Irawan and Wahyudi (2022) reported that instructional interventions effectively improve grammar skills by increasing student engagement and learning outcomes. Similarly, Flores (2023) and Impas (2021) found interactive SIMs valuable for enhancing students' grammar skills, further confirming that SIMs effectively address learning gaps and significantly improve grammatical competence.

Extent of Benefits of the SIMs in Learning Grammar

The extent to which Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) benefit grammar learning is evident in the recorded mean scores. Students demonstrated a strong understanding of conjunctions and modals ($\bar{x} = 4.92$) and reported high motivation to learn grammar ($\bar{x} = 4.92$), confirming that SIMs facilitate both comprehension and engagement. The clarity of grammar concepts ($\bar{x} = 4.85$), well-structured lessons, and simple, easy-to-follow instructions ($\bar{x} = 4.85$) further demonstrate the accessibility and usefulness of SIMs. According to Adonis (2020), respondents found SIMS to be highly effective in enhancing their understanding, engagement, and independence in learning. Respondents reported that the structured and interactive approach of SIMs made complex topics easier to grasp and more enjoyable to study.

The material is widely perceived as student-friendly ($\bar{x} = 4.85$) and engaging, making grammar lessons more interactive and accessible. Despite the lowest-rated statement ($\bar{x} = 4.62$) concerning the ability to learn at one's own pace without time pressure, it still falls within the Strongly Agree (SA) category, emphasizing that SIMs effectively support independent learning. According to Manlapig et al. (2024), respondents found the intervention beneficial in boosting their confidence, motivation, and interest in learning. Similarly, Adonis (2020) highlighted that the self-paced nature of SIMs allows students to learn at their own speed, reinforcing difficult concepts and ultimately enhancing their academic performance. These findings collectively affirm that SIMs play a crucial role in facilitating independent learning, improving comprehension, and fostering student engagement.

The low standard deviation ($SD = 0.34$) indicates consistency in student responses, suggesting a uniform positive perception of SIMs. Overall, the findings confirm that SIMs are highly effective instructional tools in teaching conjunctions and modals. The results demonstrate that these materials significantly improve students' grammar skills, enhance motivation, and create a more engaging and accessible learning experience.

The findings align with Aparicio (2024), who reported a significant improvement in post-test scores, confirming the positive impact of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) on student learning. Aparicio also emphasized that SIMs foster independent learning, allowing students to progress at their own pace and deepen their understanding. Similarly, Limbago-Bastida and Bastida (2022) observed a notable increase in students' grades, highlighting SIMs' role in enhancing academic performance. Supporting these findings, Sebulen et al. (2023) concluded that SIMs effectively helped students improve their least mastered skills, reinforcing their value in education.

Conclusions

Improving grammar proficiency is crucial in enhancing students' overall language competence and academic success, as it directly impacts their ability to communicate effectively in various contexts. This study highlighted the persistent challenges students face in mastering conjunctions and modals, which are essential grammar components. The implementation of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs), designed following Bruner's theory of instruction, provided scaffolded and contextualized learning experiences that supported students in overcoming these difficulties. These materials facilitated learner-paced instruction, which allowed students to gradually master complex grammatical concepts through clear explanations and well-organized activities.

The results of the study demonstrated significant improvements in students' grammar skills, moving from a fairly satisfactory level to an advanced level in their understanding and application of conjunctions and modals. Students also expressed strong positive perceptions of the SIMs, highlighting their role in boosting motivation and building confidence. These perceptions reinforce the role of SIMs as an effective tool in fostering positive learning experiences, extending beyond academic performance to support emotional and motivational development.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of using inclusive, learner-centered instructional materials, particularly in under-resourced educational settings. SIMs, when thoughtfully designed and aligned with curriculum goals, not only address cognitive learning gaps but also support the emotional and motivational needs of students. These materials are shown to be effective tools in improving grammar proficiency and fostering a more engaging and supportive learning environment, demonstrating the value of structured, contextualized interventions in enhancing academic outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that the use of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) be further explored and implemented in various educational settings to assess their broader applicability in improving grammar proficiency. Given the positive impact observed in this study, future research could expand the sample size and include students from diverse schools or regions to determine if these results can be generalized across different demographics and educational contexts. Additionally, future studies could adopt a comparative approach by incorporating control groups, which would enable a more robust evaluation of the effectiveness of SIMs compared to traditional teaching methods or other instructional interventions.

It is also recommended that further research explore the factors that contribute to students' perceptions of the SIMs and how these perceptions relate to their actual performance. Investigating these factors could provide valuable insights into how SIMs can be refined to better address students' needs and improve alignment between perceived benefits and academic outcomes. Furthermore, integrating SIMs with digital tools or exploring other instructional strategies could enhance the interactivity and engagement of the learning process, potentially increasing the effectiveness of the intervention.

Lastly, to enhance the generalizability of the findings, future studies could employ longitudinal designs to examine the long-term effects of SIMs on students' grammar proficiency and overall academic achievement. This approach could provide deeper insights into the sustained impact of SIMs beyond short-term improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researcher adhered to ethical guidelines and ensured full compliance with the principles of informed consent. All participants were fully informed about the nature of the study, the objectives, and the procedures involved. They were made aware of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. Anonymity was guaranteed to all respondents, and personal information was kept confidential throughout the study. The well-being of the participants was prioritized, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or discomfort.

Furthermore, no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study, as the researcher had no personal or financial stakes in the outcomes. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were appropriately cited. The interpretation of the findings was carried out impartially and without bias. Finally, the results of the study were used solely for research purposes, with the aim of contributing to the enhancement of instructional practices in grammar education.

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